

CD95 controls neuronal and vascular branching during central nervous system development

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Short title

Role of CD95 in branching

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Abstract

Development of neurons and vessels shares striking anatomical and molecular features and is presumably orchestrated by an overlapping repertoire of signaling systems. The processes and pathways involved in constructing both of these compartments however, are not fully understood. Here, we demonstrate that the CD95/CD95L signaling system contributes to both neuronal and vascular development in the central nervous system through a non-apoptotic signaling mechanisms. Induced loss of CD95 via *in utero* electroporation of the developing neocortex causes aberrant neurite growth and branching. CD95 signaling modifies the morphology of neurons by blocking the activity of GSK3 β in a PI3K- and Src-dependent manner. Similarly, in the developing vasculature of the mouse retina, loss of endothelial-CD95 reduces vessel branching and endothelial cell proliferation. Together, CD95 is identified as a receptor that mediates branch formation in both neurons and vessels. These data impacts our understanding of CD95's biology and the therapy of central nervous system disorders.

Introduction

Despite functional differences of the nervous and vascular systems, they share striking anatomical features including the highly complex and precisely branched network. This neurovascular network is established by extrinsic guidance molecules that are partially shared by nerves and vessels (Adams and Eichmann, 2010). These cues are sensed in growing neuronal processes by a specialized sensory and motor structure located at their terminal end – the growth cone (Hur et al., 2011). In sprouting capillaries, endothelial tip cells - analogously to growth cones - extend numerous filopodia to guide the growth and navigation of the nascent vessel through the tissue. The number of identified signaling systems commonly orchestrating the growth and navigation of growth cones and tips cells is increasing, including VEGF-A, Nogo-A, UNC5 and others (Adams and Eichmann, 2010; Wälchli et al., 2013). Interestingly, most of these systems are involved in axonal outgrowth and pathfinding, angiogenesis and tumorigenesis.

CD95 was initially discovered as a cell surface molecule expressed on human lymphocytes that triggers apoptosis upon stimulation with agonistic antibodies (Trauth et al., 1989; Yonehara et al., 1989). CD95 is a transmembrane type I receptor containing an intracytoplasmic death domain (DD) shared by other death receptors of the tumor necrosis factor (TNF) receptor superfamily, which is crucial for transduction of apoptosis (Scaffidi et al., 1998). Binding of CD95L to CD95 leads to recruitment of the DD-containing protein FADD (Fas associated protein with death domain) to CD95's DD (Scott et al., 2009). This eventually leads to caspase-8 activation and triggering of cell death (Dickens et al., 2012; Schleich et al., 2012). Notably, within CD95's DD there is a modified immunereceptor tyrosine-based activation/inhibitory-like motif (ITIM/ITAM) – YXXL – that is susceptible to phosphorylation through members of the

Src-family kinase (SFK). The phosphorylated Y-residue serves as recruitment platform for SH2-domain containing proteins that ultimately lead to activation of PI3K and/or ERK downstream of CD95 (Sancho-Martinez and Martin-Villalba, 2009). This non-apoptotic signaling cascade is used in different cellular systems to mediate myriad functions, such as inflammation, tumorigenesis and stem cell survival/differentiation (Martin-Villalba et al., 2013). We have previously shown that CD95 and CD95-ligand are expressed in the developing brain (Zuliani et al., 2006). This system mediates neurite outgrowth of primary sensory neurons and branching of developing hippocampal neurons *in vitro* (Desbarats et al., 2003; Zuliani et al., 2006). However, the molecular mechanisms governing CD95-induced branching or CD95's role in the developing cortex remain unknown.

The extent of CD95's function in vessels is more controversial. Both pro-apoptotic as well as pro-angiogenic functions have been described for CD95. For instance, in age-related macular degeneration, CD95L expressed on retinal pigment epithelial cells was shown to be responsible for apoptosis activation in CD95-expressing endothelial cells beneath the retina (Kaplan et al., 1999). Moreover, the anti-angiogenic molecules TSP1 and PEDF are dependent on CD95-mediated apoptosis of endothelial cells to block angiogenesis (Volpert et al., 2002). Conversely, it has been shown that local stimulation of CD95 *in vivo* using an agonistic CD95 antibody triggers inflammation and pronounced neoangiogenesis independent of apoptosis (Biancone et al., 1997). Furthermore, endothelial cells have been reported to be resistant to CD95L-induced apoptosis (Richardson et al., 1994; Sata and Walsh, 1998; Sata et al., 2000), indicating that CD95 signaling may have a different outcome in this context.

Previous *in vivo* studies of CD95 have mainly been conducted with naturally occurring mutations in the CD95 receptor or ligand (*lpr* or *gld* mice, resp.) harboring non-functional and/or reduced

levels of the two proteins. The need for tissue-specific knockout models is thus required to clarify the controversial roles of CD95.

Here, using acute tissue-specific cre recombinase-mediated knockout of CD95 in neurons or endothelial cells, we demonstrate that CD95 is specifically required for branching of neurons as well as vessels in an apoptosis-independent manner in the developing central nervous system (CNS). Thus, CD95 adds to the list of molecules orchestrating the architecture of the neurovascular network.

Results

CD95 modulates neurite branching and growth

Previous studies suggest a role for CD95 in neurite branching *in vitro* (Desbarats et al., 2003; Zuliani et al., 2006), however the phenotype of a specific loss of CD95 activity in neurons *in vivo* as well as the underlying signaling mechanisms remain elusive to date. To address this issue, we used *in utero* electroporation (IUE) of a cre plasmid in CD95^{fl/fl} embryos at gestational stage 15.5 (E15.5), during which mainly layer II/III callosal projection neurons are produced, to specifically knock out CD95 in developing neurons. Neuronal morphology of cells electroporated with a YFP (CTRL) or YFP and cre plasmid (CD95-KO) was analyzed at postnatal day two by immunofluorescence (Figure 1A and B). Importantly, total dendrite length was significantly decreased in CD95-KO neurons compared to wild type controls ($323.0 \mu\text{m} \pm 35.2$ vs. $187.1 \mu\text{m} \pm 20.2$, Figure 1C). The longest dendrite was similarly shortened in CD95-KO cells ($94.8 \mu\text{m} \pm 9.0$ vs. $54.0 \mu\text{m} \pm 3.4$, Figure 1D). Also, the number of branching points was reduced from an average of 9.8 ± 1.3 to 6.5 ± 0.8 after CD95 knockout (Figure 1E), while no change was observed in the number of primary dendrites per cell (1.5 ± 0.2 in CD95-KO vs. 1.4

± 0.2 in controls, [Figure 1F](#)). CD95^{fl/fl} cells isolated at E16, followed by *in vitro* electroporation with cre or control plasmids, and grown for 4 days *in vitro* (DIV) displayed similar morphological changes. Total neurite length, length of longest process and number of branching points were reduced in CD95-KO neurons as compared to control-electroporated counterparts ([Supplementary Figure S1A-F](#)).

Next, we wanted to address the impact of activation as well as overexpression of the CD95 receptor on dendritic morphology. CD95 was overexpressed in developing cortical neurons via IUE followed by analyses of neuronal morphology *in vivo* as well as *in vitro*. Neocortical cells were electroporated *in utero* with a control (CTRL) or a CD95-overexpression plasmid (CD95-OE) at gestational stage E15.5 and analyzed two days after birth ([Figure 1G](#)). Overexpression of the CD95 receptor in cortical neurons increased total dendritic length (CTRL: $231.0 \mu\text{m} \pm 10.9$, CD95-OE: $353.4 \mu\text{m} \pm 14.4$; [Figure 1H](#)) as well as the length of the longest dendrite (CTRL: 53.7 ± 2.9 , CD95-OE: 71.8 ± 3.0 ; [Figure 1I](#)). Interestingly, overexpression of CD95 in cultured neurons increased total neurite length to a similar extent as treatment of cells with CD95L (CTRL: $632.0 \mu\text{m} \pm 194.8$, CD95-OE: $841.8 \mu\text{m} \pm 243.9$, CD95L: $977.2 \mu\text{m} \pm 615.7$; [Supplementary Figure S1G-M](#)). Addition of CD95L to CD95 receptor overexpressing cells did not further increase neurite length over CD95-OE or CD95L treatment alone (CD95-OE + CD95L: $998.2 \mu\text{m} \pm 294.2$, [Supplementary Figure S1](#)). Loss of CD95 leads to fewer branching points in cortical and hippocampal neurons (Zuliani et al., 2006) and we thus tested if activation of CD95 can induce generation of additional branching points. CD95-OE cells contained more branching points than control cells (CTRL: 16.0 ± 0.8 , CD95-OE: 23.7 ± 1.1 , [Figure 1J](#)), while no difference was observed in the number of primary dendrites (CTRL: 2.1 ± 0.2 , CD95-OE: 2.6 ± 0.1 , [Figure 1K](#)). Together, these data indicate that stimulation of the CD95 pathway in

neuronal progenitors by either treatment with CD95L or increasing the amount of receptors per cell lead to an increase in dendritic complexity *in vitro* and *in vivo*, manifested by longer dendrites and more branching points.

CD95L induces neuronal branching through inactivation of GSK3 β

GSK3 β is a key kinase involved in the regulation of neuronal morphology and its activity can be modulated by phosphorylation (Hur and Zhou, 2010). It has been shown that CD95 stimulation can result in GSK3 β phosphorylation via the Akt pathway (Corsini et al., 2009; Kleber et al., 2008). Thus, we examined GSK3 β phosphorylation status in primary neurons upon CD95L treatment at the residue Ser-9, which inhibits its kinase activity. CD95L treatment increased Thr-308 phosphorylation of Akt as well Ser-9 phosphorylation of GSK3 β (Figure 2A, lanes 3 and 4). Apart from Akt, several other kinases are capable of inactivating GSK3 β by phosphorylating its Ser-9 residue, including P70 S6 kinase, certain isoforms of PKC, PKA and ILK. The CD95L-induced increase in phosphorylation was unaffected by incubation with PKA, PKC, or MEK inhibitors (Supplementary Figure S2A, lanes 6-8), which by themselves did not influence GSK3 β phosphorylation levels in these neurons (Supplementary Figure S2A lanes 3-5).

There is mounting evidence that PI3K regulates several aspects of neuronal morphogenesis, including elongation and guidance by inducing Ser-9 phosphorylation of GSK3 β (Hur and Zhou, 2010). Thus, we addressed the role of PI3K in CD95-induced branching. The PI3K inhibitor, LY294002, blocked CD95L-induced Ser-9 phosphorylation of GSK3 β (Figure 2A, lanes 5-7). Moreover, incubation with LY294002 blocked CD95L-induced branching of cultured neurons (Figure 2B).

Members of the Ras superfamily of small GTPases modulate PI3K activity (Castellano and Downward, 2010). These GTPases are the best characterized components controlling neuronal shape through cytoskeletal modifications (Luo et al., 1997). To study their involvement in CD95-induced branching, immunoprecipitations of RhoA, Rac or Ras in their activated forms were performed. Neither the total amount of RhoA- or Rac-GTP nor their ratios to total RhoA and Rac, respectively, were modified (Figure 2C). On the contrary, the amount of activated Ras increased upon treatment with CD95L (Figure 2C). Consistently, increased Ras activity was not found in *lpr* neurons after exposure to CD95L (Supplementary Figure S2B).

The PI3K subunit p85 binds to CD95 in the developing brain

We have previously shown that non-apoptotic function of CD95 can be mediated by recruitment of SH2-containing proteins to the tyrosine residue Y283 lying within the ITAM of CD95's death domain (Sancho-Martinez and Martin-Villalba, 2009). Members of the Src-family kinase (SFK) phosphorylate this residue allowing recruitment of different SH2-containing proteins that in turn lead to activation of the PI3K and/or ERK pathway (Martin-Villalba et al., 2013). Therefore, we investigated how CD95 is linked to activation of PI3K in the developing brain. We first tested association of SFK proteins to CD95 in brain lysates from different embryonic and postnatal stages. We found association of SFK with CD95 in immunoprecipitates from lysates from E13 to E17 telencephalic cortices (Figure 3A). Interestingly, this interaction was still found at P0 to P3, but was undetectable at P24 (Figure 3A). Thus, SFK proteins could potentially phosphorylate the Y283 residue in the death domain and thereby enable binding of SH2 domain containing proteins. In high-grade glioma and adult neural progenitors we previously found recruitment of the SH2-containing PI3K activatory subunit p85 to CD95 (Corsini et al., 2009; Kleber et al.,

2008). We therefore examined a possible interaction of p85 with CD95 in embryonic and postnatal brain lysates. p85 co-immunoprecipitated with CD95 at E14, E15 and E16, and this association was not influenced by the treatment of the lysates with CD95L, indicating that at these stages enough CD95 ligand is available *in vivo* to fully induce p85's recruitment to CD95 (Figure 3B, left panels). It is noteworthy, that this interaction was not detected in brain lysates from P1 or P3 (Figure 3B, right panels).

To further elucidate the role of SFK proteins in CD95-mediated neuronal morphogenesis, we performed knockdown of the SFK protein Src in cultured cortical neurons and measured neurite length and branching with or without additional CD95L stimulation. Src knockdown alone did not alter neurite length (scrambled siRNA: 815.3 μm , Src siRNA: 881.0 μm ; Figure 3C), the length of the longest process (scrambled siRNA: 284.6 μm , Src siRNA: 327.4 μm ; Figure 3D), or the number of branching points (scrambled siRNA: 10.2, Src siRNA: 9.6; Figure 3E). However, loss of Src effectively inhibited the CD95L induced increase in total neurite length (scrambled siRNA + CD95L: 1053.0 μm , Src siRNA + CD95L: 709.2 μm ; Figure 3C), the length of the longest process (scrambled siRNA + CD95L: 386.3 μm , Src siRNA + CD95L: 252.4 μm ; Figure 3D), and branching points (scrambled siRNA + CD95L: 16.0, Src siRNA + CD95L: 9.1; Figure 3E). The number of primary dendrites per cell was not affected by CD95L treatment or Src knockdown (Supplementary Figure S3). Interestingly, treatment with CD95L significantly affected the axonal tree but not the dendritic tree of cultured neurons (Supplementary Figure S3).

Together, these data suggest that CD95 mediates neurite growth and branching through interaction with Src and PI3K.

CD95 regulates angiogenesis in vitro

The development of the nervous and vascular systems are tightly linked. As CD95 has been shown to be expressed in endothelial cells (Sata et al., 2000), we next investigated whether CD95 may also be able to modulate vessel functions. We first confirmed that CD95 is expressed in human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) as analyzed by FACS analysis and Western blot of HUVECs (Figure 4A-B).

Next, we assessed the impact of CD95 loss on the angiogenic capacity of the endothelial cells. For this, we performed siRNA-mediated knockdown of CD95 in HUVECs (Figure 4B) and subsequently analysed their ability to form capillary-like tubes in matrigel (Figure 4C). A strong decrease in the number of tube branches (42 ± 19 vs. 11 ± 6) as well as their length (10425 ± 4206 vs. $2666 \pm 1514 \mu\text{m}$) could be observed after knockdown of CD95 with siRNA (siCD95) compared to scrambled control siRNA (siScr) (Figure 4D-E). Moreover, the number of nodes and meshes that were formed was significantly reduced after siCD95 knockdown (nodes 139 ± 121 vs. 13 ± 7 ; meshes 5 ± 4 vs. 0 ± 0 , Figure 4F-G), indicating that CD95 is required for proper tube formation.

In order to assess whether activation of CD95 on the other hand would increase branching, we stimulated HUVECs with a CD95L-coated membrane and subsequently analysed their tube formation capacity in matrigel (Figure 4H). Indeed, after CD95L treatment, HUVECs formed branches of significantly higher number (53 ± 32 vs. 113 ± 27) and length ($14598 \mu\text{m} \pm 5571$ vs. $27488 \mu\text{m} \pm 4270$, Figure 4I-J). Consistent with this, the number of nodes and meshes increased significantly after CD95L treatment (nodes 116 ± 49 vs. 236 ± 49 ; meshes 2 ± 1 vs. 6 ± 2 , Figure 4K-L). Notably, no increase of apoptosis was observed after stimulation of HUVECs with

CD95L, as examined with TUNEL staining ([Supplementary Figure S4D](#)). Thus, CD95 activation does not induce apoptosis of endothelial cells, but promote their angiogenic activity.

CD95 deletion in the developing retina decreases vessel proliferation and branching

The striking similarities of CD95's effect in neuronal and vascular branching *in vitro* prompted us to further investigate CD95's function in vessel development. The vasculature of the mouse retina develops post-natally which offers an ideal system to study angiogenesis *in vivo*. In the first seven days after birth, endothelial cell proliferation, sprouting and migration lead to the formation of the primary vascular plexus in the retina, with the vascular network extending radially from the central retina to the periphery (Pitulescu et al., 2010). During this time period, sprouting angiogenesis can be readily observed. To generate endothelial cell specific CD95 knockout mice we crossed the tamoxifen inducible Cdh5-(PAC)-CreER^{T2} mouse line (Wang et al., 2010) with CD95^{fl/fl} mice (from here on termed CD95-iECKO). Levels of CD95 were significantly reduced in FACS analysed CD31⁺ endothelial cells derived from livers of tamoxifen-induced CD95-iECKO adult mice as compared to CD95-control littermates ([Supplementary Figure S4A](#)). Using those mice we examined the role of CD95 in developing angiogenesis in the post-natal retina. For retinal angiogenesis analyses, cre was activated in newborn pups by tamoxifen injections from P1-P3 and on P5 and pups were sacrificed at P6 ([Figure 5A](#)). Blood vessel staining of whole mount retinas with Isolectin B4 (IsoB4) and subsequent quantification showed significant reduction in the area covered by blood vessels ($27.8\% \pm 3.4$ vs. $23.9\% \pm 3.2$) and in the vessel radial outgrowth from the optic nerve to the periphery ($0.71\% \pm 0.06$ vs. $0.66\% \pm 0.06$) in CD95-iECKO mice compared to CD95-controls ([Figure 5B-D](#)), indicating impaired angiogenic front progression in the primary plexus during

retinal vascularization. These defects were accompanied by a marked decrease in the number of branches (2820 ± 183 vs. 2627 ± 177 branches/vessel area) and branching points (1684 ± 122 vs. 1567 ± 112 , [Figure 5E-G](#)), similar to the abnormal branching phenotype we observed during neuronal development. To further explore the cause of the observed reduction of vessel outgrowth and branching, we analysed endothelial cell proliferation and vessel regression, two crucial aspects during the angiogenic process. Double immunostaining with the proliferation marker phospho-histone H3 (pH3) and IsoB4 showed a significantly decreased number of proliferating endothelial cells in CD95-iECKO mice compared to CD95-control mice (75 ± 22 vs. 57 ± 17 pH3⁺/IsoB4⁺ cells/vessel area, [Figure 5H-I](#)). Vessel regression was analyzed by counting collagen IV empty sleeves of basement membrane without endothelial cells. Quantification of the double immunostaining of IsoB4 and Collagen IV (ColIV) showed no difference in the number of empty sleeves between CD95-control and CD95-iECKO retinas (1.0 ± 0.3 vs. 1.0 ± 0.4 , ColIV⁺/IsoB4⁻ normalized to CD95-control, [Supplementary Figure S4B-C](#)). Altogether, these data suggest that CD95 regulates developmental angiogenesis *in vivo* by modulating endothelial cell proliferation and branching, without affecting vessel regression.

Discussion

By using tissue-specific knockout models, we show for the first time *in vivo* that the TNF receptor superfamily member CD95 is an important regulator of both neuronal and vascular morphogenesis. Our results demonstrate that CD95 activation is required for neurite growth and branching of embryonic cortical neurons as well as vessel branching and endothelial cell proliferation in post-natal retina. In neurons, neurite branching is promoted by Ras and the Src/PI3K/GSK3 β pathway. By showing the requirement of CD95 for proper development of

retinal vessels, this study also reinforces the idea that CD95 is promoting rather than counteracting angiogenesis. We propose that by utilizing its src-mediated CD95's tyrosine phosphorylation this receptor acts as a growth factor receptor stimulating branching in neurons and vessels.

CD95 signaling directly inputs into major established pathways controlling neuron and vessel fate. In neurons, we found that stimulation with CD95L increases the amount of activated Ras (Ras-GTP). GTPases, like Rho, Rac, Ras and Cdc42, are known to be powerful intracellular regulators signaling to the actin cytoskeleton (Luo et al., 1997) which were shown to regulate neurite and endothelial tip cell growth (Li et al., 2000; Luo et al., 1996; Luo et al., 1994; Ruchhoeft et al., 1999; Threadgill et al., 1997). Moreover, activated Ras has been shown to regulate neuronal polarity acting through the PI3K pathway (Yoshimura et al., 2006). Consistently, we have found that the PI3K subunit p85 associates with CD95 during neuronal development and that inhibition of PI3K abolishes CD95-dependent phosphorylation of GSK3 β , a target effector of PI3K signaling important for the establishment and maintenance of neuronal polarity and neurite length (Jiang et al., 2005; Yoshimura et al., 2005). Such an association has been already described during glioblastoma invasion (Kleber et al., 2008). Notably, these interactions decline after completion of neural development and other SH2 proteins might take over thereafter.

In vessels, we have shown that CD95 is required for proper branching and proliferation. Similar to neurons, CD95 may activate PI3K in endothelial cells, which has been shown before to trigger Rac/Rho as well as Grb2 and subsequently Cdc42, resulting in actin reorganization, filopodia formation and cell migration (Lamallice et al., 2004; Le Boeuf et al., 2004; Ruiz de Almodovar et

al., 2009). The stimulation of cell proliferation by CD95 has already been studied in other systems where CD95 activates cellular switches such as the MAP kinases Erk, JNK and p38 to promote growth (Brint et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2010). These downstream effectors may also be elicited in endothelial cells upon CD95 stimulation. Interestingly, CD95 may also support endothelial cell migration through activation of MMPs via a PI3K/GSK3 β pathway (Kleber et al., 2008), another process that is crucial for angiogenesis. The details of the molecular mechanisms in endothelial cells remain to be explored. As a cell surface receptor with intracellular kinase activity, CD95 shares the same signaling machinery with other receptor tyrosine kinases. Thus, the ability of the intracellular domain of CD95 to bind SH2-domain proteins provides a signaling hub for proliferation, migration and branching.

Other DD-containing receptors were also shown to be involved in neuronal guidance and angiogenesis. For instance, TNFR1 mediates TNF α -induced angiogenic sprouting (Sainson et al., 2008). Moreover, the DD-containing UNC5 modulates axon guidance, angiogenesis and apoptosis (Llambi et al., 2001). Similar to CD95, these opposing functions depend on DD interactions.

CD95 has long known to be expressed on endothelial cells. However, studies of its function have led to ambiguous results regarding its apoptotic or non-apoptotic role. In culture, endothelial cells have been reported to be resistant to CD95L-induced apoptosis via PI3K/AKT-mediated up-regulation of the anti-apoptotic protein FLIP (Richardson et al., 1994; Sata et al., 2000; Suhara et al., 2001). Conversely, at certain concentrations CD95 ligation can stimulate VEGF production (Marx et al., 1999) suggesting a pro-angiogenic function. Along this line, local stimulation of CD95 *in vivo* using an agonistic antibody triggers pronounced neoangiogenesis that is accompanied by infiltration of monocytes, independently of apoptosis (Biancone et al.,

1997). However, several studies of pathologies in the retinal vasculature have pointed at an apoptotic role of the CD95-CD95L system in endothelial cells. In a model of age-related macular degeneration for example, *lpr* and *gld* mice that carry a germline spontaneous mutation of CD95 or its ligand, respectively, have higher incidence of retinal neovascularization compared to wildtype mice (Kaplan et al., 1999). CD95L expressed on retinal pigment epithelial cells was proposed to activate apoptosis in CD95-expressing retinal endothelial cells. Similarly, in ischemic retinopathy, *gld* mice exhibit increased retinal neovascularization and decreased apoptosis (Davies, 2003). In this case CD95L on leukocytes was identified as trigger of endothelial cell apoptosis (Ishida et al., 2003). Moreover, during retinal development, systemic blockade of CD95L suppressed vascular pruning (Ishida et al., 2003).

These experiments showing a negative effect of CD95 on angiogenesis used either systemic administration of CD95 agonists or *lpr* or *gld* mutant mice. Thus, the fact that other CD95-related systemic effects might be at the roots of the observed phenotype could not be excluded. This misinterpretation of results has been exemplified by studies on CD95 function after spinal cord injury. First, protection against spinal cord injuries in *lpr* and *gld* mice was thought to be due to inhibition of CD95-induced apoptosis in neurons and glia (Demjen et al., 2004). However, CD95 deletion in neurons and glia did not protect against apoptosis (Letellier et al., 2010; Martin-Villalba et al., 2013). Instead the use of myeloid-specific deletion of CD95L revealed that spinal cord injury activates CD95 on myeloid cells to facilitate its recruitment to the injury site and finally cause cell death (Letellier et al., 2010). Thus, our approach of analyzing the role of CD95 in retina angiogenesis using an endothelial-specific CD95 knockout model is shedding light on this controversial issue.

Activation of CD95 during development might be similar to its activation during hypoxic disease conditions, in which mainly glial cells and microglia upregulate CD95L in order to activate CD95 signaling in both the brain and the retina (Gregory et al., 2011; Ju et al., 1995; Kim et al., 2007; Matsuyama et al., 1994; Sairanen et al., 2006). During development of the retina, hypoxic conditions induce vessel growth through factors secreted by glial cells. It is likely that CD95L is one of these factors produced by glia in response to hypoxic stimuli, leading to enhanced vessel growth as reported in our study. Similarly, CD95L expressed by glia in the developing neocortex might promote neurite branching and growth.

Upon completion of development, the interplay of endothelial and neural cells remains crucial for homeostasis. In the adult neurogenic niches, neural stem cells reside in close proximity to endothelial cells and are nurtured by factors released from the vascular niche that regulate stem cell self-renewal and differentiation (Shen, 2004; Shen et al., 2008). As the CD95-CD95L signaling system has been shown to regulate adult neural stem cell survival and differentiation (Corsini et al., 2009), it is tempting to speculate that CD95 is involved in later stages of life to regulate neural stem cell/endothelial cell interactions.

In glioblastomas, CD95 is known to activate cell migration and thereby contribute to tumorigenesis (Kleber et al., 2008). On this grounds, a phase II clinical trial with glioblastoma patients using a CD95-Fc protein to inhibit CD95's activity in combination with re-irradiation showed, for the first time since introduction of actual therapy with Temodal® 10 years ago, a significant increase of overall survival in CD95L-positive tumors (Wick et al., 2014). As glioblastoma is a highly vascularized tumor (Jain et al., 2007), the therapeutic efficacy of anti-CD95 therapies could also be partially due to effects on angiogenesis. In summary, the CD95-

CD95L system could be targeted to modulate angiogenesis/axonal regeneration in retinopathies and cancer.

Methods

Animals

CD95^{fl/fl} mice (carrying a loxP-flanked CD95 gene) were a kind gift from K. Rajewsky. Cdh5-(PAC)-CreER^{T2} mice were a kind gift from R. Adams. Bl/6-lpr mice were kindly provided by J. Tschopp. C57Bl/6 (Bl/6) mice were purchased from Jackson Laboratories (Bar Harbor, Maine). CD95^{fl/fl} mice were combined with the Cdh5-(PAC)-CreER^{T2} line (CD95-iECKO). Tamoxifen-induced cre negative littermates were used as controls (CD95-WT).

Timed pregnant mice (7 week old Bl/6, Jackson) were super-ovulated and embryonic stage assumed to be 0.5 at 9 am if vaginal plugs were detected the following day.

All animal experiments were performed in accordance with institutional guidelines of the German Cancer Research Center and were approved by the Regierungspräsidium Karlsruhe, Germany.

In utero Electroporation

In utero electroporations were carried out as described elsewhere (Saito, 2006). Briefly, timed pregnant mice were anesthetized, uterine horns were exposed by midline laparotomy and constantly wetted with warm sterile physiological saline. Embryos were injected with 1 - 2 μ l of desired DNA plasmids mixed with 0.03% Fast Green with the help of heat pulled glass capillaries (bevelled at 30°). Five electric pulses (40V, 50ms duration, 950ms interval, BioRad XCell) were applied with Tweezertrodes (Genetronics Inc.) positioned outside of the uterine

muscle at approximately 45° respective to the interaural line of the embryo. Uterine horns were replaced within the abdomen and abdominal muscle and skin incisions were closed with sutures.

Sectioning, imaging and analysis of electroporated brains

Pups were sacrificed, brains extracted and fixed in 4% PFA overnight. 100 μ m coronal sections were prepared using a vibratome. Images of YFP positive cells were obtained on a Leica SP5 confocal microscope. To compare between control and CD95-KO cortical neurons, optical stacks (80-90 slices, 1 μ m thick) of the same cortical region were acquired and analyzed using Amira software (FEI Visualization Sciences Group).

Culture of primary neurons

Primary neurons were cultured as previously reported (Banker and Goslin, 1988). In brief, the hippocampi or dorsal cortices of embryonic day 15 (E15) mice were dissected and dissociated. Cells were plated onto poly-L-lysine (PLL)-treated glass coverslips containing Minimal Essential Medium (MEM) and 10% horse serum and kept in 5% CO₂ at 36.5°C. After 4 hours, the coverslips were transferred to a 6 cm dish containing MEM-N2 with B27 supplement (Gibco). For biochemical purposes 450000 hippocampal or cortical cells were plated onto 3 cm tissue culture dishes containing MEM-N2 medium and B27 supplement. Cells were treated with the following reagents: Self-made Leucine Zipper-CD95 ligand (LZ-CD95L; 100 ng/ml) (Walczak et al., 1999), CD95L-T4 (Kleber et al., 2008), commercially available CD95 ligand (CD95L; 400 ng/ml; Sigma) and an agonistic antibody to CD95 (Jo2; 10 μ g/ml; Becton and Dickinson). The following inhibitors were used: MEK1 inhibitor (PD98059; 200 nM; New England Biolabs), PI3K inhibitor (LY294002; 10 or 20 μ M; Calbiochem), and PKA and PKC inhibitor peptides (1.2 μ M; Upstate Biotechnology). Neurons were incubated with the inhibitors 30 min (PD98059,

PKA, PKC inhibitors) or 60 min (LY294002) prior to treatment with CD95L. For knockout, knockdown, or overexpression experiments in cultured neurons, brains were either first electroporated *in utero* (see above) and 24h later cells were isolated as described above, or cells were electroporated using the Neon® transfection system (Invitrogen) before plating. Cells were treated with CD95L 4h after plating or left untreated and fixed for further analysis after 4DIV. For siRNA mediated knockdown of mouse Src, siRNAs (Thermo Scientific ON-TARGETplus) targeting the following sequences were used: GCUCGUGGCUUACUACUCC, UCAGAUCGCUUCAGGCAUG, GGGAGCGGCUGCAGAUUGU, GCACGGGACAGACCGGUUA.

Immunocytochemistry, imaging, and statistical analysis of neuron morphology.

Neurons were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde at 37°C for 15 min and permeabilized in 0.1% Triton X-100 for 5 min. After blocking with 2% fetal bovine serum, 2% bovine serum albumin and 0.2% fish gelatine dissolved in PBS, cells were incubated with primary antibodies against mouse anti-tubulin-III- β and anti-Tau-1 (Chemicon). Immunoreactivities were visualised with a antibody coupled to rhodamine or fluorescein isothiocyanate (Amersham). Neurons were observed with the inverted fluorescence microscope IX81 from Olympus. All image analyses was performed with Cell^R software from Olympus. For morphological measurements, at least 20 individual neurons per group were analysed. Statistical analysis was performed using unpaired two-tailed t-test. Data from at least three independent experiments were used for statistical analysis.

Protein extraction and immunoblotting

Cells were harvested, washed in chilled PBS, resuspended and homogenized in a buffer consisting of 0.2% SDS, phosphatase inhibitors (NaF, NaN₃, pNPP NaPPi, β-glycerophosphate, 10 mM each) and protease inhibitor (complete, Roche). Lysates were centrifuged at 10000 x g for 10 min at 4°C and boiled for 5 min in Laemmli buffer. Proteins were resolved by SDS-PAGE followed by Western blotting to nitrocellulose membranes. Membranes were blocked with 5% Skim Powder Milk in PBS-Tween (PBS plus 0.05% Tween-20) for 1 h and then probed with the following antibodies: anti-CD95 (1:1000; Cell Signalling), anti-GSK3β (1:1000; Santa Cruz), anti-phospho-GSK3β (1:1000; Cell Signalling), anti-ERK 1/2 (1:1000; Transduction Lab), anti-phospho-ERK 1/2 (1:1000; Santa Cruz), anti-GAPDH (1:1000, Santa Cruz), and phospho-Src family (Tyr416) antibody (1:200, Cell Signaling). Immunoreactive proteins were visualised with peroxidase-conjugated anti-rabbit or anti-mouse antibodies (Santa Cruz) and enhanced chemiluminescence detection kit (Pierce Biotechnology) by exposure to Kodak X-Omat films. Results are representative of three independent experiments.

Immunoprecipitation from brain tissue

Neurons from different embryonic and postnatal days were isolated following the same procedure as for cell culture. Cell suspensions were centrifuged at 1500xg and pellets resuspended in lysis buffer (20mM Tris pH.7.8; 150mM NaCl; 10% glycerol; 1% Nonidet p40; 2mM EDTA) supplemented with protease and phosphatase inhibitors (protease inhibitor cocktail, Roche; 1 mM sodium orthovanadate) and incubated for 30' on ice. 500 μg of total protein were precleared with an isotype antibody (biotinylated Hamster IgG₂, λ₂; BD Bioscience) and monomeric avidin beads (Sigma) at 4°C over night. Samples were centrifuged at

8000 rpm 5 min at 4°C. Supernatants were incubated at 4°C with either 5 µg biotinylated anti-CD95 or 5 µg of the matching isotype (biotinylated Hamster IgG) over night. Afterwards, 40 µl of avidin beads were added and in samples incubated for another 3 hours. Beads were washed 5 times with 20 volumes of lysis buffer. 40 µl of 2x Laemmli buffer were added to beads and heated to 95°C for 5' followed by SDS-PAGE and Western blotting (see above).

Determination of activated cellular Rho, Ras and Rac

Neurons either treated with CD95L (100 ng/ml) or left untreated were lysed in magnesium lysis buffer (MLB; 25 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 10 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM EDTA, 2% glycerol, and 5 µg/ml of each leupeptin and aprotinin). The amount of activated cellular Rho, Ras and Rac were determined by precipitation with a fusion protein consisting of GST and the Rho-binding domain of Rhotekin (GST-Rhotekin), the Ras-binding domain of Raf-1 (GST-RBD) or the p21-binding domain of human PAK-1 (GST-PBD; Upstate Biotechnology) as described (de Rooij and Bos, 1997; Ren et al., 1999). GTPases were detected using monoclonal antibodies against RhoA (1:200; Santa Cruz Biotechnology), Ras (1:1000; clone 10, Upstate Biotechnology) and Rac (1:1000; Upstate Biotechnology).

Culture of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs)

HUVECs (Lonza) were maintained in endothelial basal medium-2 (EBM-2, Lonza) supplemented with EGM-2 SingleQuot Kit Supplements and Growth Factors (Lonza). Cells were kept in 5% CO₂ at 36.5°C and used up to passage 5 for experiments.

siRNA-mediated knockdown in HUVECs

For siRNA-mediated knockdown of endothelial cells, HUVECs were plated on a 6-well-plate.

On the next day, 50 nM siRNA targeted against CD95 (On-TARGET plus Human FAS SMARTpool, Dharmacon) (GAACAUGGAAUCAUCAAGG, UGGAAGGCCUGCAUCAUGA, UGAGGAAGACUGUUACUAC, GCGUAUGACACAUUGAUUA) was transfected using Lipofectamine 2000 (Life technologies) according to manufacturer's protocol. Non-targeting scrambled siRNA (ON-TARGET plus Non-targeting pool, Dharmacon) was used as a control. siRNA knockdown was performed for 48 hours before the experiment.

Endothelial tube formation assay

The endothelial tube formation assay was performed according to Arnaoutova et al., 2009. Briefly, 80 μ l of growth factor reduced matrigel (BD) were plated in each well of a 96-well plate and allowed to gel at 37°C for 30min. For CD95L stimulation, HUVECs were stimulated for 4 hours on control- or CD95L (CD95L-T4) coated lipid membranes. Subsequently, 15 000 stimulated HUVECs or HUVECs treated with siRNA were put on the gelled matrigel in EBM (Lonza) supplemented with 35 ng/ μ l bFGF (Relia Tech). Triplicates were made for each condition. Tube formation was assessed after 12 hours of incubation and Calcein AM (Life technologies) was used to visualize the tubes. Microscopy was performed on a Zeiss Cell Observer (Observer.Z1) with 4x objective. Tubes were analyzed with the ImageJ plugin Angiogenesis Analyzer (<http://image.bio.methods.free.fr/ImageJ/?Angiogenesis-Analyzer-for-ImageJ>). Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Statistics were performed using unpaired two-tailed t-test.

FACS analysis

HUVECs were detached from cell culture flask with trypsin and washed twice with PBS. Blocking was performed with 10% FBS in PBS for 30min. Subsequently, HUVECs were stained with APC-conjugated anti-CD95 (Apogenix) and FITC-conjugated CD31 antibody (ebiosciences) for 1 hour. Unstained and single stained cells were used as controls. After washing three times with the blocking solution, cells were analysed on a BD FACS Canto II machine. Data were analysed with FlowJo.

Retina analysis

Newborn CD95-control or CD95-iECKO pups were intragastrically injected with 50 μ g of tamoxifen (Sigma T5648) in 50 μ l peanut oil/10% ethanol at postnatal days P1, P2, P3 and P5. At P6, mice were sacrificed, eyeballs were isolated and fixed in 4% PFA on ice for 2 hours. Retinas were isolated and blocked with 0.3% Triton X-100/1% bovine serum albumin in PBS for 2h at room temperature (RT). The retina vasculature was stained with Alexa568-conjugated Isolectin B4 (IsoB4, Invitrogen I21412, 1:250), anti-collagen IV antibody (Novotec, ref. 20451, 1:100) and anti-pH3 antibody (Cell Signalling, ref. 97015, 1:100) diluted in blocking solution, overnight at 4 °C and subsequently incubated with appropriate Alexa labeled secondary antibodies for 2h at RT. Afterwards retinas were flat mounted and imaged. Pictures were taken using a confocal microscope Zeiss LSM 510 and image analysis was accomplished with Fiji (ImageJ). The endothelial cell coverage (vessel area) was calculated as IsoB4⁺ area per retina area. Branching and branching points were counted and normalized to total vessel area per retina. For the analysis of endothelial cell proliferation, pH3⁺/IsoB4⁺ endothelial cells were counted and normalized to vessel area. Vessel regression analysis was accomplished by counting

ColIV⁺IsoB4⁻ structures (empty sleeves) and correlating them to retina vessel area. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD. Statistics were performed using unpaired two tailed t-test.

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Author Contributions

S.C., R.H., C.Z., C.R.A., A.M.V. designed the research, S.C., R.H., R.Y., H.H., C.Z. performed the experiments and analyzed the data; G.S.G. produced reagents and contributed to experiments and S.C. and R.H. wrote the manuscript.

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Figure legends

Figure 1: CD95 is required for appropriate development of neuronal morphology.

A. Treatment scheme for **B-K** and illustration of *in utero* electroporation (IUE) and tissue processing. IUE of neocortex with pCAG-YFP (CTRL), pCAG-YFP together with pCAG-Cre (CD95-KO), or pCAG-YFP-CD95 (CD95-OE) plasmids was performed at E15.5.

B, G. Representative photomicrographs and illustrations of neurite tracing of CTRL (left two panels in B and G), CD95-KO (right two panels in B) and CD95-OE (right two panels in B) neurons. Scale bars = 10 μ m.

C-F. Quantification of total dendritic length (**C**), length of the longest dendrite (**D**), the number of branching points (**E**), and the number of dendrites (**F**) in control (n=10) and CD95-KO neurons (n=14) from at least 3 different pups.

H-K. As in **C-F**, with control (n=28) and CD95-OE (n=37) neurons from at least 3 different pups.

Data are shown as mean and individual data points. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, unpaired two tailed student's t-test.

Figure 2: CD95 inhibits GSK3 β activity in developing neurons

A. Activation of CD95 leads to phosphorylation of GSK3 β via PI3K. Primary hippocampal neurons from E16 embryos were treated with 20 or 40 ng/ml CD95L with or without the PI3K inhibitor LY294002 (10 μ M). Lysates were subjected to Western blot analysis for Thr308 phosphorylated Akt (P-Akt-Thr308), total Akt (T-Akt), Ser9 phosphorylated GSK3 β (P-GSK3 β), and total GSK3 β (T-GSK3 β).

B. The number of branching points per cell was assessed at 4DIV in hippocampal neurons treated with the indicated concentration of CD95L (24h) alone or after pre-incubation (30 min) with the PI3K inhibitor LY294002 (10 μ M).

C. Activation of CD95 leads to elevated Ras-GTP levels. Hippocampal neurons were treated with CD95L (100 ng/ml) and subsequently tested for immunoprecipitated Rac-GTP, RhoA-GTP and Ras-GTP levels by Western blotting. Cell lysate levels served as loading controls. *non-specific band, arrow: specific band for Ras.

Figure 3: CD95 interacts with PI3K in the developing brain

A. Brain lysates from E13-17 and P0, 1, 3 and 24 were immunoprecipitated with a CD95 antibody or isotope control (iso). Membranes were probed with antibodies against SFK and CD95.

B. Lysates from E14 - E16, P1 and P3 brains were immunoprecipitated as in **A**, and blotted for p85 and CD95. Additionally, cells were treated with CD95L (20 ng/ml) for 30 minutes before lysis or left untreated.

C-F. Down-regulation of Src inhibits CD95L-induced neurite outgrowth and branching. E16 cortical neurons were electroporated with scrambled or Src specific siRNA and treated with CD95L (20 ng/ml) for 24 hours or left untreated. Representative images and tracing are shown in panel **F** (Scale bar = 20 μ m). Quantification of total neurite length (**C**), the longest process (**D**), and the number of branching points (**E**) in the four conditions. Data are shown as mean and individual data points. **p<0.01, ***p<0.001; one-way ANOVA & Tukey's multiple comparison test.

Figure 4: CD95 regulates endothelial cell branching *in vitro*

A. HUVECs were immunostained with anti-CD31 and anti-CD95 antibodies and analysed by FACS. Histogrammes of unstained (grey) vs. CD95-stained (orange) CD31-positive HUVECs are shown.

B. Lysates from untreated, scrambled siRNA (siScr) and siRNA targeting CD95 (siCD95) treated HUVECs were subjected to Western blot analysis for CD95. GAPDH was used as a loading control.

C. HUVECs were transfected either with siScr or siCD95 for 48h and assessed in an endothelial tube formation assay. Representative images of Calcein AM stained endothelial tubes and tracing of branches are shown. (red dots: nodes; yellow/green/dark blue lines: branches; blue circles: meshes)

D-G. Quantification of number of branches (**D**), total branches length (**E**), number of nodes (**F**) and number of meshes (**G**) of HUVECs subjected to siScr or siCD95.

h. HUVECs were stimulated with either control or CD95L-coated membranes for 4 hours and assessed in an endothelial tube formation assay. Representative images of Calcein Am stained endothelial tubes and tracing of branches are shown.

I-L. Quantification of number of branches (**I**), total branches length (**J**), number of nodes (**K**) and number of meshes (**L**) of control and CD95L stimulated HUVECs.

Scale bars = 500 μ m, *p<0.05, **p<0.01, unpaired two-tailed student's t-test, data are shown as mean \pm standard deviation.

Figure 5: CD95 deletion in the early postnatal retina results in vessel branching and proliferation defect

A. Experimental scheme. CD95-iECKO were used to specifically delete CD95 in endothelial cell. Pups were subjected to tamoxifen from P1-P3 and at P5, sacrificed at P6 and vessel growth in the retinas was analysed.

B-D. Representative images of CD95-WT and CD95-iECKO retinas stained with IsoB4 (red) (**B**) and the quantification of the area covered by endothelial cells (n=19 vs. n=32 retinas) (**C**) as well as the vessel radial outgrowth to the periphery (n=16 vs. n=28 retinas) (**D**). Data are expressed as percentage of total retina area (left graph) or total lobe length (right graph). Scale bars = 500 μ m.

E-G. Representative images of vessel branches in retinas of CD95-WT and CD95-iECKO mice stained with IsoB4 (red) (**E**). The number of branches and branching points are quantified (n=17 vs. n=27 retinas) (**F-G**). Data are expressed as number of branches/vessel area (**G**) or number of branching points/vessel area (**F**).

H-I. Representative images of vessel proliferation (IsoB4 in red, pH3 in green) (**h**) and quantification of proliferating (pH3⁺) endothelial cells (**I**) in CD95-WT (n=12) and CD95-iECKO (n=17) retinas. Data are expressed as pH3⁺/IsoB4⁺ endothelial cells (EC)/vessel area. Scale bars = 100 μ m. Data are shown as mean \pm standard deviation. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, unpaired two-tailed student's t-test.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: CD95-dependent neurite growth and branching in developing neurons.

A. Experimental scheme for **C-F**. E15.5 neurons from dorsal telencephalon were isolated and electroporated with either pCAG-YFP or pCAG-YFP together with pCAG-Cre plasmid. 2×10^5 cells were plated and grown for four days before subjected to immunocytochemistry.

B. Western Blot of DIV4 wild type (left and middle lane) or CD95^{flx/flx} (right lane) cortical neurons electroporated with an empty vector (EV, left lane), pCAG-CD95 (OE, middle lane), or pCAG-Cre (KO, right lane) plasmid.

C. Representative photomicrographs of control or CD95-KO neurons after 4 DIV (upper panels) and corresponding neurite tracing (lower panels). Scale bar = $20 \mu\text{m}$.

D-F. Quantification of total neurite length (**D**), length of the longest process (**E**), and number of branching points (**F**) of control (n=38) and CD95-KO neurons (n=39). **p<0.01, ***p<0.001, unpaired two tailed student's t-test.

G. Experimental scheme for h-m. 24 hours after IUE of E15.5 embryonic brains with either pCAG-YFP (ctrl) or pCAG-YFP-CD95 (CD95-OE) plasmids, cells were isolated and cultured. Cells were either left untreated or treated with 400 ng/ml CD95L for 92 hours before analysis. CC = timepoint when cell were isolated and taken into cell culture.

H-L. Quantification of total neurite length (**H**), longest process (**I**), axonal tree length (**J**), number of branching points (**K**), and number of dendrites (**L**) of control (n=31), CD95L treated control (n=13), CD95-OE (n=31), and T4 treated CD95-OE (n=32) cells after 4 days in vitro. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001; one-way ANOVA & Tukey's multiple comparison test.

M. Representative photomicrographs (left panel) and neurite tracing with AMIRA software (right panel). Scale bar = $20 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure S2: CD95 inhibits GSK3 β activity in developing neurons

A. Activation of CD95 leads to phosphorylation of GSK3 β . Primary cortical neurons were cultured for 2 DIV and treated with CD95L (40 ng/ml), PKA inhibitor (1.2 μ M), PKC inhibitor (1.2 μ M), or MEK1 inhibitor (200 nM) alone (lanes 1-4), or with combinations of CD95L and inhibitors (lanes 5-8) for 30 minutes. Lysates were tested with antibodies against total and phosphorylated Erk (T-Erk and P-Erk1/2), total and phosphorylated GSK3 β (T-GSK3 β and P-GSK3 β), and Actin.

B. Ras-GTP levels are not increased in *lpr* mice after CD95L stimulation. Hippocampal neurons of wild type (WT) or *lpr* mice were treated with CD95L (100 ng/ml) and subsequently tested for immunoprecipitated Ras-GTP levels by western blotting. Cell lysate levels served as loading controls.

Figure S3: Down-regulation of Src inhibits CD95L-induced neurite outgrowth and branching increase.

A-C. E16 cortical neurons were electroporated with scrambled or Src specific siRNA and treated with CD95L (20 ng/ml) or left untreated. Representative images are shown in main figure 3, panel f. Quantification of axonal tree length (**A**), dendritic tree length (**B**), and the number of primary dendrites (**C**) in the four conditions. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; one-way ANOVA & Tukey's multiple comparison test. **D.** Confirmation of Src knockdown in cultured hippocampal neurons. Cells were electroporated with scrambled (CO) or Src specific (KD) siRNA and subjected to SDS-PAGE and Westernblotting after 4DIV.

Figure S4: Branching defect of CD95-deleted retina vessels is not due to vessel regression

A. CD95 is deleted upon Tamoxifen injection in CD31⁺ population of the liver of adult CD95-iECKO mice compared to control littermates, as measured by FACS (MFI: mean fluorescence intensity).

B. Representative images of “collagen empty sleeves” as indicated by IsoB4 (red) negative and ColIV (green) positive stainings in CD95-WT and CD95-iECKO mice. White arrowheads point to ColIV⁺/IsoB4⁻ empty sleeves.

C. Quantification of vessel regression in retinas of CD95-WT and CD95-iECKO mice. (n= 7 vs. n=15). Data expressed as number of ColIV⁺/IsoB4⁻ empty sleeves /vessel area (h). Data are shown as mean ± standard deviation. Scale bars = 100 μm.

D. TUNEL staining of control- or CD95L-stimulated HUVECs shows no difference between the groups. Data are shown as mean± standard deviation. Unpaired two-tailed student’s t-test

Supplementary Methods:

TUNEL staining

For TUNEL staining, HUVECs on CD95L-coated membranes were fixed using 1% PFA and stained using the DeadEndTM Fluorometric TUNEL system kit (Promega) according to manufacturer’s protocol. Cells were counterstained with DAPI.

Figure 1

Figure 2

A PI3K dependent GSK3 β signaling

B

C Ras activation in 2DIV primary neurons

Figure 3

Figure 4

A

B

C

D

E

F

G

H

I

J

K

L

Figure 5

A

B

C

D

E

F

G

H

I

Figure S1

Figure S2

A *GSK3 β* activation in 2 DIV primary neurons

CD95L	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
PKA inhibitor	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-
PKC inhibitor	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-
PD98059	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+

B *Ras* activation in *lpr* neurons

Figure S3

Figure S4

